

from Bangladesh (IRGC 103835 and IRGC 105316) and a cross between *O. sativa* and *O. nivara* (IRGC 105316), which showed less than 30% infection (Table 2) based on visual scores and ELISA, could be considered as potential resistance donor lines. Because *O. nivara* is susceptible to BPH, the resistance could be against the virus.

References

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Green leafhopper-susceptible advanced lines resistant to rice tungro viruses

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Eight rice varieties and lines susceptible to green leafhoppers were tested in field plots in Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, and Midsayap, North Cotabato, for their reactions to tungro viruses. IR26, TKM6, Utri Merah, IR69705-1-1-3-2-1, IR69706-1-4-2-5-2-2, IR73889-5-1-1-1-1-2, IR1561-228-3-3, and TN1 (control) were tested during the 1996 wet season (WS), 1997 dry season (DS), and 1997 WS cropping. They were planted in 4 × 4-m plots laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. All rice hills were scored

visually for disease incidence at 30 and 60 d after transplanting (DAT).

Leaf samples of each entry from five quadrats in an × pattern with nine hills each were also taken in all replicates in the same period for enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) to determine the presence of rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). Each leaf sample was crushed in a leaf and bud press (Eijkelpamp Agrisearch Equipment, The Netherlands) and leaf sap was extracted with 1 mL of 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7) containing 0.15 M NaCl and 0.05% Tween 20. For ELISA, the microtiter plate (Costar, Cambridge, MA) was coated by immunoglobulin (courtesy of IRRI) at 0.5 µg mL⁻¹ for RTBV and 1 µg mL⁻¹ for RTSV. The immunoglobulin-alkaline phosphate conjugate was diluted 1,000 times for RTBV and 500 times for RTSV. For each plate, four wells were set aside for the extracts of healthy TN1 leaves, along with one well for extracts of RTBV + RTSV-infected TN1 leaves and one well with the extraction buffer for the control. The presence of tungro viruses in the extracts was determined by measuring the absorbance at 405 nm in a MicroELISA reader (Bio-Rad 3550). Absorbance of more than twice the mean of four healthy control readings was considered positive.

At the Nueva Ecija site, very low tungro incidence based on symptoms was recorded at 30 DAT during the three seasons (data not shown). Because of the very low disease incidence observed and the limited supply of antiserum, the 1996 WS and 1997 DS samples, taken at 30 DAT at this site, were not tested by ELISA.

The ELISA results of the 1997 WS samples taken at 30 DAT also showed low rates of RTBV + RTSV and RTBV infection. During this period, more infection by RTSV alone than by RTBV + RTSV and RTBV alone was recorded in most entries and was significantly high in TN1. Increased infection by either RTSV and RTBV or both was observed in all entries at 60 DAT. IR26, TKM6, Utri Merah, IR69705-1-1-3-2-1,

and IR69706-1-4-2-5-2-2 showed significantly lower infection by RTBV + RTSV compared with other entries. The 1996 and 1997 WS trials had higher rates of RTBV + RTSV infection at 60 DAT than the 1997 DS trial where infection by mostly RTSV alone was obtained (see table). This confirmed previous observations of low tungro incidence in the DS and at the early stage of crop growth, especially in areas with a low level of disease pressure.

In North Cotabato during the 1996 and 1997 WS trials, significantly higher RTBV + RTSV infection on TN1 was obtained as early as 30 DAT. More single infections of RTSV or RTBV, rather than dual infection, were obtained at 30 DAT in the 1997 DS trial, with significantly higher infection by RTSV alone observed on TN1 than on other test entries. This again showed the prevalence of dual infection during the WS crop. Although higher tungro infection occurred at 30 DAT in North Cotabato than in Nueva Ecija, Utri Merah and its derivatives, IR69705-1-1-3-2-1 and IR69706-1-4-2-5-2-2, maintained their low infection even at 60 DAT regardless of season (see table). IR26 and TKM6 recorded high RTBV + RTSV infection at 60 DAT during the 1997 DS and 1997 WS trials, in contrast to their low infection in Nueva Ecija during the same period, indicating that these varieties succumbed to tungro under high disease pressure or presence of a virus strain that can infect these varieties. During the trials, visual scoring of the plants was difficult at 60 DAT due to the effects of rice black bug (*Scotinophara coarctata* F.) infestation, which severely damaged the plants, especially in the 1996 WS trial, in which most plants died.

The average yield of 3.6 t ha⁻¹ of IR69705-1-1-3-2-1 during the 1996 WS trial in Nueva Ecija was not significantly different from the 4.0 t ha⁻¹ yield of IR26 (a high-yielding variety). Similarly, IR69706-1-4-2-5-2-2 yielded 4.0 t ha⁻¹ in the 1997 DS trial at the same location. These results showed that the yield of test varieties is on a par with that of a high-yielding variety when

Percentage of RTBV (B) and RTSV (S) infection^a as detected by ELISA on test lines and varieties at 30 and 60 DAT, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, and Midsayap, North Cotabato, 3 cropping seasons, 1996-97.

Location/test entry	1996 WS						1997 DS						1997 WS					
	30 DAT			60 DAT			30 DAT			60 DAT			30 DAT			60 DAT		
	B+S	B	S	B+S	B	S	B+S	B	S	B+S	B	S	B+S	B	S	B+S	B	S
<i>Muñoz, Nueva Ecija</i>																		
IR26				4 a	25 c	8 a				0 a	0 a	1 a	0 a	1 a	2 a	0 a	11 b	2 a
TKM6				3 a	15 b	6 a				0 a	0 a	15 a	0 a	3 a	1 a	2 a	11 b	4 a
Utri Merah		No		3 a	9 ab	25 ab		No		0 a	0 a	1 a	0 a	1 a	0 a	0 a	14 b	0 a
IR69705-1-1-3-2-1		ELISA		0 a	1 a	0 a		ELISA		0 a	0 a	10 a	0 a	0 a	7 ab	0 a	0 a	11 ab
IR69706-1-4-2-5-2-2	x ^b	x	x	x	x	x				0 a	0 a	67 b	0 a	0 a	6 ab	0 a	1 a	25 bc
IR73889-5-1-1-1-1-1-2	x	x	x	x	x	x				0 a	0 a	10 a	0 a	0 a	10 ab	0 a	0 a	81 d
IR1561-228-3-3				30 b	5 ab	43 b				0 a	1 a	12 a	1 a	1 a	13 b	14 a	0 a	72 d
TN1				67 c	6 ab	26 ab				2 a	0 a	58 b	9 b	7 b	38 c	54 b	2 a	39 c
<i>Midsayap, North Cotabato</i>																		
IR26	17 a	17 a	11 a	-	-	-	0 a	1 a	1 a	81 d	14 ab	3 ab	60 cd	36 d	2 a	93 c	7 a	0 a
TKM6	12 a	13 a	7 ab	-	-	-	0 a	7 a	7 a	54 c	17 ab	14 bc	54 c	25 c	4 a	82 bc	8 a	4 ab
Utri Merah	2 a	14 a	0 a	4	14	7	0 a	3 a	0 a	3 ab	4 a	17 cd	7 a	11 b	3 a	12 a	10 a	2 a
IR69705-1-1-3-2-1	0 a	8 a	0 a	1	7	3	0 a	2 a	0 a	1 a	0 a	1 a	1 a	10 ab	2 a	1 a	7 a	1 a
IR69706-1-4-2-5-2-2	x	x	x	x	x	x	2 a	4 a	2 a	1 a	6 a	6 abc	0 a	4 ab	4 a	4 a	13 a	9 b
IR73889-5-1-1-1-1-1-2	x	x	x	x	x	x	1 a	0 a	1 a	13 b	6 a	27 d	35 b	0 a	41 b	79 b	17 a	0 a
IR1561-228-3-3	- ^c	-	-	-	-	-	1 a	3 a	4 a	43 c	27 b	7 abc	68 d	26 c	3 a	87 bc	12 a	0 a
TN1	47 ^d b	7 a	40 b	-	-	-	2 a	1 a	39 b	88 d	9 a	1 a	87 e	2 a	4 a	90 bc	10 a	0 a

^aFrom 123 to 180 plants test entry¹ season¹. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P = 0.05$, Duncan's multiple range test). ^bNot included in the 1996 WS trial. ^cPlants severely damaged by Malayan black bug. ^dSamples include IR1561-228-3-3.

grown in an area with low tungro pressure. The yield of all test entries in North Cotabato was drastically reduced by rice black bug infestation. In the 1997 DS trial, IR69705-1-1-3-2-1

and IR69706-1-4-2-5-2-2 yielded an average of 1.9 and 0.9 t ha⁻¹, respectively. The latter was significantly higher than the 0.7 t ha⁻¹ yield of IR26. The low tungro virus infection and the

relatively high yield of these advanced lines showed their potential use as stop-gap planting materials for tungro disease management. ■

Stress tolerance — excess water

Inheritance of submergence tolerance at the early seedling stage in rainfed lowland rice

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In the early seedling stage, mostly under direct-seeded conditions, lowland rice varieties are subjected to submergence because of erratic rainfall distribution and prolonged water stagnation. As a result, crop establishment is poor and productivity is low. Tolerance for submergence is therefore a highly desired trait of rainfed lowland varieties.

We studied the inheritance of submergence tolerance in four crosses

Segregation ratio for submergence tolerance in F₂ generation of different crosses.

Cross	Submergence score		Seedlings in F ₂ (no.)		χ^2	Ratio	Probability
	Parents	F ₁	T ^a	S			
FR43B (T)/ IR42(S)	2.6 (T) 8.5 (S)	4.0 (T)	151	104	0.911	9:7	0.5-0.3
FR43B (T)/ Pankaj (S)	2.6 (T) 9.0 (S)	4.2 (T)	147	108	0.201	9:7	0.7-0.5
Rahaspanjar (T) IR42 (S)	3.6 (T) 8.5 (S)	4.5 (T)	140	115	0.187	9:7	0.7-0.5
Rahaspanjar (T) Pankaj (S)	3.6 (T) 8.8 (S)	4.9 (T)	142	113	0.033	9:7	0.9-0.8

^aT = tolerant, S = susceptible.

involving two tolerant (T) varieties—FR43B and Rahaspanjar—and two susceptible (S) varieties—IR42 and Pankaj. Seeds of parents, F₁s, and F₂s of each cross were raised in galvanized-iron trays (70 × 60 × 15 cm) filled with clay soil on polythene sheet. Twenty

lines with 15 seedlings line⁻¹ were grown in each tray. Both parents and their F₁s were grown in a single line each, whereas the rest of the populations were raised in RCBD with three replications.

Thirty-five-day-old seedlings were completely submerged in an artificial